

D2.3 Second short report of cluster events

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Table of contents

List of acronyms	6
Executive Summary	7
1. Cluster event rationale	8
1.1. Context	8
1.1.1. EC policies and initiatives for research data practices and infrastructures	8
1.1.2. The importance of data infrastructures and practices in CS	8
1.2. Objectives	8
2. Key takeaways on strengthening data infrastructures, practices, and services in CS	9
Takeaway #1: Focusing on enhancing data literacy before introducing more data analysis tools	9
Takeaway #2: Facilitating connections with creative communities for data visualisation	10
Takeaway #3: Raising awareness of the challenges of SSH citizen science data	10
Takeaway #4: Providing better guidance and support on data ethics and management	11
Takeaway #5: Maintaining a balance between wide accessibility and simplicity in data services	11
Takeaway #6: Exploring further the relationships between CS and data altruism	12
3. Conclusion and next steps	12
References	14
Annex A – Detailed agenda of the ECS Cluster Event 2024	15
Annex B – Speaker biographies and summaries of their presentations	17
Annex C – Profile of registrants and attendees	20
Annex D – Visual outputs of group activities	21

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Expansion
CS	Citizen science
EC	European Commission
ECS	European Citizen Science
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
R&I	Research and Innovation
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The 'Second short report of cluster events' is Deliverable 2.3 (D2.3) from the EU-funded project European Citizen Science. This deliverable is part of WP2 entitled 'Strengthening links and collaboration,' which has the overall objective to strengthen and expand the citizen science community.

More specifically, this deliverable is part of Task 2.5, 'Strengthening collaboration through harnessing resources and outputs from EU, national and regional CS initiatives'. It focuses on one of the activities of T2.5, which is to organise yearly online cluster events involving projects, networks and European Commission representatives to engage in discussions centred around a unifying theme in the field of CS.

This document highlights the key insights gathered from the second annual cluster event, which took place online on April 25th, 2024. The event, titled "Strengthening Citizen Science in Europe: The Role of Data Infrastructures, Practices, and Services", attracted approximately 52 attendees across Europe. Key points for reinforcing data infrastructures, practices, and services in citizen science included providing more guidance and support in data management and ethics, raising awareness of the challenges of CS data in social sciences and humanities, and providing more training over tools for data analysis.

The document is presented in the following order:

Section 1 introduces the rationale and the objectives of the second cluster event. Section 2 elaborates on six key takeaways of the cluster event drawn from the speakers' presentations and the participatory activity. Finally, section 3 gathers some concluding remarks and next steps. The

annexes include a detailed agenda of the event, details of the projects presented along with the speakers' biographies, information on the profile of the attendees, and a selection of visual output resulting from the activities carried out throughout the event.

1. Cluster event rationale

1.1. Context

1.1.1. EC policies and initiatives for research data practices and infrastructures

The European Commission (EC) promotes citizen and societal participation in research and innovation (R&I) for several reasons: it boosts excellence by improving both the quantity and quality of data collected; it enhances effectiveness through the development of collective capabilities; and it fosters greater societal trust in science by promoting transparency (EC, 2020). To capitalise on these benefits, the EC has initiated various efforts focused on research data practices and infrastructures over the last decade. For example, under Horizon Europe, specific open science mandates require beneficiaries to manage research data responsibly, adhering to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles (EC, 2021). Another key initiative is the establishment of the [European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC), a system for researchers in Europe to store, share, process, analyse and reuse, within and across disciplines and borders, FAIR research outputs, such as research data, publications, and software. More specifically, EOSC is deployed as a network between data repositories and services of research infrastructures and other scientific service providers to develop a trusted federation of research data and services for R&I in Europe (EC, 2023).

1.1.2. The importance of data infrastructures and practices in CS

A common thread that runs through almost all CS initiatives is their collection and generation of data. With the expanding scope of these projects, we are seeing an unprecedented increase in data. When transformed into knowledge, this data is invaluable for deepening our understanding of scientific and social phenomena and for its crucial role in informing evidence-based policy-making. However, the transition from raw data to knowledge depends on several factors. Key among these is the application of good data practices and the establishment of comprehensive data infrastructures.

Moreover, for the CS community, embracing the principles of open science, open data, and adhering to the FAIR standards are crucial steps, among other strategic approaches, to fully capitalise on citizen-generated data. The [Mutual Learning Exercise on Citizen Science Initiatives - Policy and Practice](#) notes the importance of using CS data in research, policy-making, and decision-making. However, challenges such as managing the data well and ensuring it meets FAIR and other ethics standards to maximise its excellence and impact still need to be addressed. (EC, 2022)

1.2. Objectives

In this context, the European Citizen Science (ECS) project, an initiative that fosters a vibrant CS community, sought to provide a space for discussing the importance of strengthening data practices and infrastructures

within the European CS landscape. The lead partner for this task, Stickydot, srl, coordinated, organised, and moderated an online event to host a diverse group of speakers on the subject of data. This event served as a platform to deepen understanding of key issues related to data practices, services, and infrastructures, and it allowed participants to consider how these insights could meet the specific needs, challenges, and objectives of their citizen science projects. The event targeted a broad audience, including academics, educators, CS practitioners, data scientists, developers, early-career researchers, policy makers, civil servants, industry representatives, and the general public.

The online event took place on April 25th, 2024 (for the programme schedule and list of invited speakers and their biographies, refer to Annex A and Annex B). The key objectives of this event were to:

- To promote networking between the citizen science community and EU representatives.
- To provide a space to exchange practical experiences and lessons learnt around the topic of data, more specifically, data practices, services, and infrastructures.
- To understand and highlight the needs of the CS community in terms of data practices, services and infrastructure and thus help shape the work CSIC is doing in the ECS project (e.g., for the development of Citizen Science Data Acquisition Infrastructures).

This report compiles takeaway messages for all stakeholders involved, directly or indirectly, in this subject, outlining ways of strengthening data infrastructures, practices, and services in CS.

2. Key takeaways on strengthening data infrastructures, practices, and services in CS

This year's ECS Cluster event delved into the nexus of CS and data infrastructures, services, and practices. It featured an array of perspectives from a diverse set of stakeholders, including CS practitioners, early-career researchers, and representatives from the EC (see Annex C). During the first part, the event was structured around different subtopics presentations, such as data altruism, data management and ethics, platform development and services, and infrastructures in citizen social science and humanities data. In contrast, the second part was dedicated to a group discussion activity (see Annex D). From these presentations and discussions, six key takeaway messages were distilled on how to reinforce data infrastructures, practices, and services in CS. These insights are intended to be useful to a broad spectrum of stakeholders, not exclusively to any specific group but encompassing all those engaged in CS, research, data sciences, and beyond.

Takeaway #1: Focusing on enhancing data literacy before introducing more data analysis tools

The CS community has highlighted a need for better data analysis and visualisation capabilities. This includes giving different groups of stakeholders the ability to work and play with data effectively. Alongside this, there

was a strong emphasis on improving data literacy to ensure that these stakeholders and communities involved in CS projects can use data more effectively and confidently. According to a participant of the event, there are stakeholder groups that are heavily invested and affected by the data generated in CS projects, and thus, giving them the ability to work with data can be very helpful for them. In other words, although numerous data analysis tools are currently available, the essential task in the CS landscape involves a concerted effort to build capacity. This foundational work is crucial for ensuring that citizens, researchers and organisations have the necessary skills and knowledge on data analysis and visualisation to effectively use these tools.

Datathons were mentioned in the discussion as a great way to enhance data literacy and data analysis capabilities among citizens in CS projects since they provide participants with practical, hands-on experience in working with data. Moreover, datathons provide access to real and relevant datasets that participants might not otherwise encounter. This exposure can help demystify data analysis and make this concept more tangible and understandable, and finally, it might improve their ability to read, understand, create, and communicate data as information.

Takeaway #2: Facilitating connections with creative communities for data visualisation

During the group discussion, the need to foster collaborative relationships between citizen science projects with creative and artistic communities, like with visual designers, emerged as a key priority. Encouraging such collaborations can lead to more innovative and engaging ways to visualise and interpret data. For instance, [Domestic Data Dreamers](#) is a research and design studio that has successfully partnered with organisations to drive change through a blend of data, community involvement, and artistic expression. To enhance these partnerships, one could explore hosting joint workshops, setting up art-science exhibitions, offering artist residencies focused on CS projects, and creating shared spaces for artists and CS experts to collaborate on interdisciplinary projects. These efforts can enrich the understanding and impact of data generated by CS projects through creative visualisation and design.

Participants of the event also shared data visualisation tools they liked to use such as [Data Wrapper](#) and [RAWGraph](#). With that in mind, and building on the first takeaway above, data visualisation tools have their benefits, but integrating them with the creativity of artists can transform “basic” data into compelling visual stories and information. This can more likely capture the attention and improve the understanding of the broader audience, turning mere numbers into meaningful narratives.

Takeaway #3: Raising awareness of the challenges of SSH citizen science data

CS within the social sciences and humanities (SSH) involves generating and managing data, yet this area often receives less focus compared to natural/environmental sciences such as biodiversity and ecology. In SSH, CS data presents unique challenges that require more attention from the CS community: data frequently appears in local languages and varies across formats, including text, images, audio, and video, and open and free tools for transcribing and translating these data are quite limited. Moreover, there are often more subjective observations from participants that may be misinterpreted, notes can be unclear, and there is a pressing need for greater consistency, as well as more extensive data sets that contain qualitative data. Another challenge

highlighted by participants at the cluster event relates to the sharing of SSH data from CS projects. Specifically, there is a need for secure public databases that can store large amounts of data, such as video and audio, and that can offer tailored access levels to users outside the institution that owns the data.

The visibility of infrastructures and services that manage data generated from participatory activities in the SSH remains limited within the CS landscape. Enhancing this visibility is crucial. One effective strategy to achieve this could be to foster greater collaboration between the SSH and CS communities. Establishing dedicated working groups, organising targeted workshops, and promoting joint projects could serve as vital platforms for knowledge exchange and integration. Additionally, promoting joint publications and hosting interdisciplinary conferences could further bridge the gap between these disciplines, enabling a more seamless flow of information and resources. The conference [Connect. Collaborate. Cocreate](#) held in October 2023, is a good example of this strategy. This approach not only enriches both fields but also amplifies the impact of CS initiatives across various academic and practical domains of the SSH.

Takeaway #4: Providing better guidance and support on data ethics and management

Inadequate data management, publication practices, and ethical practices often limit the potential to use and reuse CS data. In fact, while data management documentation can increase understanding of and trust in CS data, improve data quality and accessibility, and increase the reproducibility of research studies, it was found in a study that 62% of a total of 56 CS projects did not use a DMP, mainly due to lack of time or resources (Thuermer et al., 2023). Many projects lack the necessary skills and insights to tackle these issues, which explains why there was a clear need expressed by the audience during the cluster event for better training, guidance, support, and best practices to address these challenges. Moreover, projects often find it difficult to understand the terms related to data privacy policy, data use, and data ownership, especially when projects involve citizens from different countries with various laws and regulations. When thinking about solutions, it was clear to the participants of the event that there is no need to start from scratch and reinvent the wheel since standards like FAIR and GDPR already exist; they just need to be better explained and applied within CS projects.

Takeaway #5: Maintaining a balance between wide accessibility and simplicity in data services

When developing a data collection service, such as a large-scale participatory monitoring platform, as is quite common in CS, it is crucial to find the right balance between making the service accessible to a wide audience (Bonnet et al., 2023) and keeping its operation simple. This balance can be illustrated through various features and strategies. In terms of accessibility, it is beneficial for the platform to be freely available, not requiring users to create an account, and to provide an intuitive interface. These features help lower barriers for users who may not be tech-savvy. Additionally, creating an offline version of the platform allows users to participate without a constant internet connection, and translating the platform into over 50 languages ensures that it is accessible to a global audience. On the technical side, achieving this balance requires a solid IT backbone. The use of low-energy AI models helps in processing data efficiently while keeping operational costs down. Keeping the size of the stored data manageable ensures that the system remains responsive and sustainable. By

integrating these elements, the platform can serve a broad user base effectively while maintaining simplicity in its operations, making it both user-friendly and technically robust.

Takeaway #6: Exploring further the relationships between CS and data altruism

CS and data altruism have a lot in common and one could say that CS both supports and relies on data altruism. This concept of data altruism refers to:

“the voluntary sharing of data on the basis of the consent of data subjects to process personal data pertaining to them, or permissions of data holders to allow the use of their non-personal data without seeking or receiving a reward that goes beyond compensation related to the costs that they incur where they make their data available for objectives of general interest as provided for in national law, where applicable, such as healthcare, combating climate change, improving mobility, facilitating the development, production and dissemination of official statistics, improving the provision of public services, public policy making or scientific research purposes in the general interest” (Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council).

In that context, data altruism and organisations recognized under the Data Governance Act can support CS research projects (such as in the health and environmental field). These entities enable individuals to participate in scientific research by generating, gathering, and analysing data. The [DATALOG](#) project is a key example of that and is an established legal entity developed with the goal of empowering citizens to take ownership and decisions on the consumption data from their utilities (water, electricity, gas) to promote responsible consumption, fight energy poverty and foster sustainability (Maccani et al., 2024). This approach allows individuals to understand their consumption habits in detail, compare them with others, and realise the impact of their actions on their city. This awareness fosters a community spirit focused on jointly combating climate change. The way DATALOG connects data and citizens is well-considered and serves as a great example for the CS community. The concept of data altruism, as demonstrated by DATALOG, could inspire CS to adopt similar models that increase data transparency and encourage public participation in research, ultimately driving a stronger communal effort towards sustainability.

3. Conclusion and next steps

This document presents a short report of the second cluster event under T2.5 of WP2 of the ECS project. The objective of this report is to highlight the takeaways drawn from various presentations and group discussions of the event. These takeaways can serve as a useful resource for a wide range of stakeholders, including CS practitioners, early-career researchers, data scientists, back and front-end developers and policy makers, who are interested in the topic of data infrastructures, services and practices in CS. Moreover, there will be one final cluster event for 2025. This event will coincide with the yearly launch of the eu-citizen.science platform, showcasing new features.

These key takeaways will be useful in shaping the work of WP3 “Enhancing digital skills for FAIR and open science communities”, which is currently under development. The objectives of WP3 are to coordinate and support collaborative spaces towards FAIR and open developments. This means developing the concept of “open and FAIR data with open and FAIR tools” through: (i) Mapping existing experiences of collaborative development to set the best practices of development for CS data services and infrastructures, (ii) Providing and improving collaborative spaces for co-design and development of services, (iii) Connect CS initiatives with e-infrastructures (in particular EOSC) through the collaborative development of data/metadata services.

Furthermore, the ECS community continues with the ECS Collaboration Group, which includes over 60 diverse initiatives, including both large-scale and smaller projects from different parts of the globe. The group convenes monthly to discuss various topics related to CS. These recurring meetings serve as a networking, resource-sharing, and support platform for all CS initiatives across the EU and beyond.

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Annex A – Detailed agenda of the ECS Cluster Event 2024

Location: Online

Time (CEST)	Content
9.00 - 9.05	<p>Welcome Florence Gignac, Stickydot</p>
9.05 - 9.45	<p>Introductory talks (including Q&A)</p> <p>EC policies and initiatives for research data practices and infrastructures Michael Arentoft, Head of Unit, Open Science and Research Infrastructures, DG Research & Innovation, European Commission</p> <p>The Web of FAIR Research Data Karel Luyben, President of the EOSC Association</p> <p>Datalog as the first EU Recognized Data Altruism Organization Giovanni Maccani, Research Director, Ideas for Change</p>
9.45 - 9.50	<p>Short energizer Florence Gignac, Stickydot</p>
9.50 - 10.10	<p>Overview of the ECS project and its objective in enhancing digital skills for FAIR and open science communities (including Q&A) Carolina Doran, ECSA and Amalia Cardenas, CSIC/ECS</p>
10.10 - 10.20	<p>Coffee break</p>
10.20 - 11.00	<p>Talks from the citizen science community (including Q&A)</p> <p>Advantages and difficulties of developing and maintaining participatory science platforms for large-scale biodiversity monitoring Dr. Pierre Bonnet, Botanist, CIRAD, BIOS Dept., UMR AMAP and Scientific coord. of the PI@ntNet citizen science platform</p> <p>Challenges for ethical data practices in citizen science Dr. Gefion Thuermer, Head of Research - Open Data Institute</p> <p>Data infrastructures and services for citizen science from a social sciences and humanities standpoint Alessia Smaniotto, Citizen Science officer, OPERAS</p>

11.00 - 11.05	Short energizer <i>Florence Gignac, Stickydot</i>
11.05 - 11.15	Coffee break
11.15 - 12.00	Shaping data services and infrastructures to the needs of the citizen science community in Europe: A participatory activity Allocated time for attendees to discuss their needs and challenges in relation to: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Data analysis and visualisation (Breakout room 1)• Services and infrastructures for qualitative data (Breakout room 2)• Data ownership, policies and ethics (Breakout room 3).
12.00 - 12:05	Short break
12.05 - 12:25	Interactive outcome sharing
12:25 - 12:30	Closing remarks

Annex B – Speaker biographies and summaries of their presentations

Speaker	Presentation summary
<p>Michael Arentoft was previously Deputy Head of International R&I Cooperation Strategy, Innovation Union policy officer, Acting Head of Strategy for ICT R&I, Sector Head of ICT R&I Work Programme and Planning, coordinator of ICT Essential Technologies and Infrastructures, and project officer in High Performance Computing and Networking. Before joining the EC, he was with Computer Resources International and with Roving International. His educational background is from the University of Pennsylvania’s Computer and Information Science PhD program and from the Technical University of Denmark’s Electrical Engineering Master’s program.</p>	<p>EC policies and initiatives for research data practices and infrastructures. A key driver of new R&I practices is open science. Key foci include access to research data ‘as open as possible as closed as necessary’, research data that is FAIR, and the responsible management of research data, as well as open collaboration including citizen and societal engagement. EC support to enablers of open science practices notably include the European Open Science Cloud as a federation of infrastructures for the sharing and reuse of FAIR data and services, as well as ensuring that open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught.</p>
<p>Karel Luyben is Rector Magnificus Emeritus of the Delft University of Technology as of 2018. He was Rector Magnificus of the Delft University of Technology from 2010 till 2018. Before that he served as Dean of the Faculty of Applied Sciences for almost 12 years. In 1983 he was appointed full professor in Biochemical Engineering at the Delft University of Technology, and from there has gained experience in research, starting a SME, research leadership and leading European organisations like the European Federation of Biotechnology, CESAER and now the European Open Science Cloud Association. Presently he is primarily active in the domain of Open Science. Until 2023 he was National Coordinator for Open Science in the Netherlands. He was the Chairman of the Board of the Dutch Techcentre for Life Sciences for ten years and is involved with the Open Science Task Forces of CESAER and EUA and since 2020. Since 2021 he is the President of the European Open Science Cloud Association (EOSC-A).</p>	<p>The Web of FAIR Research Data. Only if data become globally Findable, Accessible, and Interoperable, we make them effectively Reusable for science and innovation, even if not all information can be publicly disclosed, such as personal data and data in industry. This asks researchers a conscious effort towards curating, storing, and sharing research data so that they are accessible to all, of course, as far as legally permissible, and ethically justifiable. This transparency also makes research results better verifiable. The benefits of researchers opening their data and research results are welcomed by decision- and policymakers, funding bodies and society at large. How does this vision of Open and FAIR research data, and the services and infrastructure needed for this, become a reality in Europe and globally? The "European Open Science Cloud" (EOSC) initiative, aiming to combine data and research infrastructures in Europe, will be explained.</p>

Giovanni Maccani is currently Research Director at Ideas for Change. Giovanni has been Assistant Professor/Lecturer in Management Information Systems at the School of Business, National University of Ireland Maynooth (NUIM). Giovanni has achieved a bachelor's and a master's degree in Engineering, both at the Polytechnic University of Milan. He earned a PhD in Information Systems at NUIM under the "Enterprise Partnership Scheme" of the Irish Research Council (IRC) in 2016, co-funded by Intel Corporation. His research domains cover the concepts of Smart Cities, Data Governance, Citizen Science, IT Governance, Design Science, Autonomous Vehicles, and Open Data. Since then, Giovanni has worked on digital transformation strategies and IT Governance across several city councils in Ireland and internationally and led several EU projects. So far, he has published more than thirty peer reviewed academic papers.

Datalog as the first EU Recognized Data Altruism Organization This presentation will cover the foundations of DATALOG, the first EU-recognized data altruism organisation. It will focus on sharing the experiences of establishing this emerging legal entity and its positioning in the emerging data altruism ecosystem enabled by the EU's Data Governance Act. DATALOG is a legal entity established in Barcelona, Spain, that promotes data sharing from citizens on utility consumption. It addresses both individual and collective purposes. The ultimate goal of the initiative is to empower people and organisations in sharing their water, gas, and electricity consumption data to collectively tackle energy poverty and fight climate change as a common good.

Dr. Pierre Bonnet is a permanent scientist at CIRAD in France, based in AMAP lab (a Joint Research Unit for plant architecture, specialised in tropical botany and bioinformatics). His topics of interest are Botany, plant ecology, and applied computer science. He got his Ph.D. in 2008 from the University of Montpellier, after two and half years of activities in South East Asia, in close collaboration with the National Herbarium of the Netherlands and the National University of Laos. Since 2009, he works as a scientific coordinator of PI@ntNet initiative, in close collaboration with scientists and engineers of INRIA, INRAE, and IRD, in order to promote citizen science for gathering new data on plants at world scale.

Advantages and difficulties of developing and maintaining participatory science platforms for large-scale biodiversity monitoring. Nearly 15 years ago, a French research consortium took on the challenge of making plant species identification easier for as many people as possible. The goal was to improve society's ability to identify biodiversity at large spatial and taxonomical scales. The developments of social networks, smartphones and machine learning techniques have largely contributed to the evolution of the PI@ntNet platform, which is now widely used by civil society (with more than 20 million users per year) and the scientific community, notably through several national and European projects such as the Gardien and Mambo initiatives. This presentation will highlight the strengths and constraints encountered throughout the development of this platform, and share some of the points to watch for future comparable initiatives.

Dr Gefjon Thuermer is the Head of Research at the Open Data Institute, and a Research Fellow at

Challenges for ethical data practices in citizen science Citizen science projects have grand

King's College London. She is the technical and scientific coordinator of IMPETUS, a Horizon Europe coordination and support action that provides resources, support and recognition for citizen science initiatives across Europe. She holds a BA in cultural sciences, and an MSc and PhD in Web Science. Her research is interdisciplinary by default, focuses on the intersection of people, data and technology, and aspires to enable inclusive engagement wherever people use technology to achieve goals together. Gefion has previously worked in citizen science with the ACTION project, where she developed a toolkit for citizen science, and on data innovation in MediaFutures and Data Pitch, where she developed toolkits for data innovation and data sharing, respectively.

ambitions and huge potential for impact; their data can contribute to a plethora of challenges society faces, through direct action, but also by informing policy-makers and institutes, and by being joined up in larger studies by researchers. However, this potential is limited by practices in data management and publication, as well as ethical challenges, which projects may not have the necessary skills and insights to fully address on their own. This talk will summarise recent research in this space, highlighting key challenges citizen science projects and those attempting to use their data face, as well as considerations for citizen science data managers, and practices that, if adopted, could significantly increase usability and impact of citizen science data.

Alessia Smaniotta develops and coordinates R&D projects for the French infrastructure OpenEdition in the field of participatory research. She is a member of the coordination team of the European OPERAS infrastructure, as Citizen science officer. She coordinated the three-year European project COESO (coeso.hypotheses.org), that developed a dedicated platform to support participatory research involving the social sciences and humanities disciplines: VERA (vera.operas-eu.org). Graduated in philosophy, journalism and sociology between Italy and France, she holds a PhD in philosophy of social sciences from the École des Hautes Études en Sciences Sociales (EHESS).

Data infrastructures and services for citizen science from a social sciences and humanities standpoint

Citizen science and participatory research can look different in social sciences and humanities (SSH) than in other disciplines, and so it is for the “data” that need to be managed in these research activities. Participatory research activities within the SSH mostly deal with human creations and phenomena, thus often handling personal information and sensitive data. As in the health domain, data reusability and FAIRification calls for special attention, as data sharing practices often happen within confidentiality restraints – both for legal reasons as well as for the purpose of sustaining trust-based interpersonal relationships. Furthermore, the relevance of multilingualism in SSH research, and the importance to embed and contextualise the “data” into a comprehensive output, also highlight the relevance of considering and preserving the specificities of the diverse research domains within the SSH. The availability of infrastructures and services addressing SSH citizen science needs not only can affect how participatory practices are carried out, but also can affect if and how they are “visible” in the citizen science landscape.

Annex C – Profile of registrants and attendees

The event registered a total of 113 participants. The actual number of attendees was 52. To the question “Do you have any previous experience with CS?” the 113 registrants responded as follows: No (n = 15, 13%), Yes, some experience (n = 73, 65%), Yes, a lot of experience (n = 25, 22%)

Profile: The profiles that resonated most with the individual registered (with the option to select multiple) - with 87 answering the question were:

Profile	Number of individual registered*	% of individual registered*
Civil society/Non-governmental organisation (international)	5	4%
Civil society/Non-governmental organisation (national)	3	3%
Civil society/Non-governmental organisation (regional or local)	1	0.8%
Education/training organisation	8	7%
General public/citizen	3	3%
General public: Learner/student	3	3%
Industry or business partner	5	4%
Media, journalist or communicator	2	2%
Policy-makers, institutions and authorities (EU level)	1	0.8%
Policy-makers, institutions and authorities (national)	1	0.8%
Research: Early-career researcher	16	14%
Research: Participant in a citizen science project/Community researcher	12	11%
Research: Scientist or belonging to the research community	27	24%
Software developer	2	2%

*The “number of attendees” column reflects the number of responses per attendees. For example, 41 attendees selected “Research: Scientist or belonging to the research community”. The “% of attendees” column reflects the average number of responses per attendees (multiplied by 100). For example, 38% of the attendees selected “Research: Scientist or belonging to the research community.”

Annex D – Visual outputs of group activities

Florence Gignac + 2 + 3d

Breakout room 1: Data analysis and visualisation

Moderators: Jorge Barba and Amalia Cardenas

What are the challenges you are facing? I struggle to/with...

Tools for data analysis and visualization

Excel Jamobi software similar to SPSS, helps with basic analysis.

Data Wrapper and rawgraphs.io is also used. Some tools on how to work with API's would be helpful.

Figuring out the different biases that databases could have was important.

Other additional tools

Stakeholders don't know that the data is available, and they don't have the time to dig into it. Having the data be available in a more user friendly way is a main challenge.

Training citizens in data visualization

There are stakeholder groups that are heavily invested/ affected by the data that is being generated. Giving them the ability to work with open data can be very helpful for them.

Data is being generated, but very few people are doing anything with the data. There are some reports that are generated from time to time, but often times they report basic information.

What needs do you have in relation to this topic? I need...

Needs

Training and connections with other communities. Such as journalists because they can help with visibility in the public sphere and can help give visibility to a project.

Data literacy is also an important aspect that needs to be considered. There is a lot of work at the fundamental level.

Things such as this call for data literacy is very important to help build an understanding on how to work with data.

Call: European policy experimentations (ERASMUS-EDU-2024-POL-EXP)
EU Grants: Call document (ERASMUS): V1.0 – 30.11.2023
Priority 3: Data literacy strategies in primary and secondary education
Deadline: 04/06/2024. 17.00 CET
Duration: 24 to 36 months

Having data literacy be connected to real-world challenges is important.

As a group, explore potential solutions that could tackle these challenges or meet those needs.

datanuggets.org

Data Nuggets | Bringing authentic research and data into K-16 classrooms

This is an important resource that teachers can use to start engaging students.

Data Nuggets are free classroom activities, co-designed by scientists and teachers, designed to bring contemporary research and authentic data into the classroom. Data Nuggets feature a scientist role model and the story of what inspired their research. In a Data Nugget activity, students are guided through the entire process of science, including identifying hypotheses and predictions, visualizing and interpreting data, supporting claims using data as evidence, and asking their own questions for future research. Because of their simplicity and flexibility, Data Nuggets can be used throughout the school year and across grades K-16, as students grow in their quantitative abilities and gain confidence. Data Nuggets have the potential to improve the

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abc Breakout room 2: Services and infrastructures for qualitative data

Moderators: Marius Oesterheld and Blanca Guasch

What are the challenges you are facing? I struggle to/with...

+

Sharing social science data

Secured public databases able to store high size data (video, audio), and capable to provide adapted access levels to users outside the institution

♥ 0 💬 0

👤 Añadir comentario

Tools

Transcribing audio recordings

♥ 0 💬 0

👤 Añadir comentario

open source tools

not-for-profit tools that allow handling secured information and that can be used in a collaborative manner (cloud stored)

♥ 0 💬 0

👤 Añadir comentario

Manual

Translating from different languages

♥ 0 💬 0

👤 Añadir comentario

Mistakes

Since observations come from people, there can be spelling mistakes or other misunderstandings when collecting data

What needs do you have in relation to this topic? I need...

+

Free and OS tools

Validated OS tools to translate and transcribe recordings

♥ 0 💬 0

👤 Añadir comentario

Analysis

The need of analysing big sets of data - it is not as easy as quantitative data

♥ 0 💬 0

👤 Añadir comentario

Consistency

Processes to help manage consistency

♥ 0 💬 0

👤 Añadir comentario

Find the most appropriate tools

♥ 0 💬 0

👤 Añadir comentario

As a group, explore potential solutions that could tackle these challenges or meet those needs.

+

Developing open source tools and/or keep sustaining the ones that already exist

For transcribing recordings

♥ 0 💬 3

👤 Anónimo 4d

Have a repository of all the open resources that already exist

👤 Anónimo 4d

Framadate to search for google suite alternatives

👤 Anónimo 4d

Invest in open infrastructure initiative. They have this discovery tool: <https://infrfinder.investinopen.org/solutions>

👤 Añadir comentario

Recognize the need for funding for data storage (especially when it comes to large files - images, videos etc.)

♥ 0 💬 1

👤 Anónimo 4d

especially for the SSH!!

👤 Añadir comentario

provide basic trainings information

♥ 0 💬 0

👤 Añadir comentario

A reflection

Not a solution, but a reflection: why is it so important to separate qualitative vs. quantitative data? In the

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Breakout room 3: Data ownership, policies and ethics
Moderators: Stefanie Schuerz and Carolina Doran

What are the challenges you are facing? I struggle to/with...

- Engaging citizens in developing and maintaining suitable and inclusive data policies
- Knowledge on what type of licenses work with different types of data
- Communication and feedback
With citizens in different languages, different laws or regulations at country level... Difficult to articulate. Also difficult to find the right channels or messages to reach the citizens
- Differentiating between legal / privacy obligations (e.g. GDPR) and good data practices (e.g. Open Science)
- Working with a variety of data licences (to meet the different expectations of participants) can generate a degree of complexity in the workflows implemented

What needs do you have in relation to this topic? I need...

- Its not clear in projects who the data belongs to. Wording on this is always ambiguous. So the need is to have clearer documentation
- Guidance, training, support
Maybe a forum or a working groups to share needs and concerns, tools, etc. We all are facing the same challenges with our data
- Templates and guidance for data ethics & privacy practices
Ideally alongside / distinct from guidance on data management & publication. I think most CS project struggle to understand the difference, and SO MANY assume a privacy policy helps their participants understand data use, ownership etc.
- Not reinventing the wheel

As a group, explore potential solutions that could tackle these challenges or meet those needs.

Trainings, guidance, support, best practices

- Anónimo 4d
Some solutions and guidance are already there, but it needs to get to the people who need it → it needs to be findable and accessible
- Anónimo 4d
We need awareness to solve the problem
- Anónimo 4d
we need trainings
- Anónimo 4d
Existing channels: ECSA WG on Data
- Anónimo 4d
eu-citizen.science is a good hub, but it might not have the functionality to nurture discussion on this → forum section or a common part on the platform could be helpful. People need to know it exists and then contribute to it.
- Anónimo 4d
<https://eu-citizen.science/resource/321>
- Anónimo 4d
ECS Ambassadors help link to different communities in European countries that work very differently
- Anónimo 4d
<https://eu-citizen.science/resource/159>
- Anónimo 4d
"Train the trainer" → scientists are not always the best trainers / educators → institutional policies need to better recognize high skill competences to the capacity of training citizens, translating scientific methodologies, goals, etc. for better exchange.
- Anónimo 4d
development of toolkits that is actionable

